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A remarkable new species of *Rhagio* Fabricius, 1775 from the Iberian Peninsula (Diptera: Rhagionidae)

Una nueva y singular especie de *Rhagio* Fabricius, 1775, de la Península Ibérica (Diptera: Rhagionidae)

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ABSTRACT: A new species of *Rhagio* Fabricius, 1775 is described from the Iberian Peninsula. It has been found at higher altitudes in the mountains of Spain and Portugal. The wing venation of the new species is remarkably variable. The new species is compared with other similar species. *Rhagio niger* (Wiedemann, 1820) and *Rhagio funebris* (Meigen, 1820) are redescribed. A lectotype is designated for *Rh. niger*. A key for all European species of *Rhagio* with darkened wings and abdomen is provided.

KEY WORDS: Iberian Peninsula, Spain, Diptera, Rhagionidae, *Rhagio*.

RESUMEN: Se describe una nueva especie de *Rhagio* Fabricius, 1775, de la Península Ibérica. La especie ha sido encontrada a elevadas altitudes en áreas montañosas de España y Portugal. La venación alar de la nueva especie es sorprendentemente variable. Se compara la nueva especie con otras similares. Se describen *Rhagio niger* (Wiedemann, 1820) y *Rhagio funebris* (Meigen, 1820). Se designa un lectotipo para *Rh. niger*. Se proporciona una clave con todas las especies europeas de *Rhagio* que presentan alas y abdomen oscuros.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Península Ibérica, España, Diptera, Rhagionidae, *Rhagio*.

Introduction

The family Rhagionidae is a relatively small family of Diptera in the infraorder Tabanomorpha (WIEGMANN *et al.*, 2011) with about 17 genera recognized worldwide (KERR, 2004). When defined in the stricter sense, i. e. without the Athericidae and Vermileonidae, the family is monophyletic (KERR, 2004; 2010). The typical genus is *Rhagio* Fabricius, 1775, characterized by the presence of two apical ventral spurs on hind tibia, an open anal cell and the antenna, which consists of three segments and a long arista (MAJER, 1997). The Palearctic Rhagionidae have been revised by LINDNER (1925) and SZILÁDY (1934). Since then, the family has got little attention in the western Palearctic. ROZKOŠNÝ & SPITZER (1965) described the genitalia of the Central European species and NARCHUK (1988) introduced some new ideas in a key to the species of the European part of the former Soviet-Union. The most recent checklist for the Palearctic region

is by MAJER (1988). CARLES-TOLRÁ (2002) lists 21 species of Rhagionidae for the Iberian Peninsula, of which 14 species belong to the genus *Rhagio*.

In this article we describe a conspicuous new species of *Rhagio*, found by the second author near Segovia (Spain) in numbers. The species is unusually dark, thus superficially resembling a species of *Ptiolina* Zetterstedt, 1842. This genus, however, has only one apical spur on hind tibia and a much shorter arista. Due to the general dark appearance and darkened wings, the Segovian *Rhagio* keys out to *Rhagio niger* (Wiedemann, 1820) in the existing keys, described from Portugal. However, there are several inconsistencies. Therefore, we have investigated the type and have concluded that the Segovian *Rhagio* is clearly distinctive. We describe it here as *Rhagio aterrimus* spec. nov., redescribe the little-known *Rh. niger* and the related species *Rhagio funebris* (Meigen, 1820) and provide diagnostic features for other species of *Rhagio* with darkened wings and dark abdomen.

Materials and methods

The terminology for the body parts used follows OOSTERBROEK *et al.* (2005), those for the male genitalia follows ROZKOŠNÝ & SPITZER (1965). It should be noted that their illustrations are based on extracted genitalia. In situ, some structures such as the hypandrium, epandrium and eighth sternite are partly or largely covered and not visible.

A matter of special relevance is the abdominal build, especially the anterior sternites. The first sternite is located just behind the hind coxae. The presence or absence of hairs on the first sternite is an important feature to distinguish the males of species within the genus *Rhagio* (NARCHUK, 1988). The second sternite is split into two parts: a smaller anterior part and a larger posterior part (Fig. 1). This split of the second sternite has also been found in Therevidae (HAUSER, 2005). In *Rhagio*, to our knowledge, the anterior part is always bare and the posterior part always hairy.

Fig. 1: Male *Rhagio* Fabricius, 1775, lateral view. 1: first sternite; 2a: anterior part of second sternite; 2p: posterior part of second sternite.

Photos of the habitus of the types of *Rh. aterrimus* have been taken using a Leica DFC420 C camera adapted to a Leica M80 binocular microscope; those of the lectotype of *Rh. niger*, using a Nikon 105 mm macro lens with extension tubes and macro flashes; those of the female *Rh. funebris*, using a Nikon D700 and a Tamron SP AF 90 mm f/2.8 DI macro lens 1:1; all the results have been digitally enhanced. Photos of heads and genitalia of *Rh. aterrimus* and *Rh. niger* have been taken by using a separate phototube on the stereomicroscope. Focal depth has been enhanced by stacking several images using the software program CombineZ (HADLEY, 2014).

The acronyms for collections used follow EVENHUIS (2016).

CTZS	-	Netherlands, Soest, private collection Th. Zeegers
NHMW	-	Austria, Wien, Naturhistorisches Museum Wien
MNCN	-	Spain, Madrid, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales
MNHN	-	France, Paris, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle
ZMHB	-	Germany, Berlin, Museum für Naturkunde der Humboldt-Universität

Species account

Taxonomic accounts: A new species of *Rhagio* is described and two species are redescribed. The three species are photographed in high resolution. Two similar species are briefly commented on.

Class Insecta Linnaeus, 1758
 Order Diptera Linnaeus, 1758
 Infraorder Tabanomorpha Hennig, 1948
 Family Rhagionidae Samouelle, 1819
Rhagio Fabricius, 1775

Rhagio Fabricius, 1775: 761

Type species: *Musca scolopacea* Linnaeus, 1758 (design. Latreille 1810: 443)

Note: According to the Code (INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON ZOOLOGICAL NOMENCLATURE, 1999), *Rhagio* should be treated as masculine.

Rhagio aterrimus sp. nov.

Figs. 2-7 and 15b

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:0CCA3130-F96A-4416-9DBC-7A20A0015484

Fig. 2: *Rhagio aterrimus* sp. nov. Male in its natural habitat, Puerto de Navacerrada, Segovia, Spain, 26-V-2015, (ÁLVAREZ, 2015).

<http://www.biodiversidadvirtual.org/insectarium/Rhagio-aterrimus-Zeegers-y-Alvarez-Fidalgo-2016-img754075.html>

Diagnosis: Black species, including abdomen, legs, palpus and halter, scutum with a pair of greyish vittae, often indistinct, wings darkened. Hairs on parafacialia, occiput, palpus, thorax and apical abdominal segments black. Anepisternum with a large field of black hairs on posterior third (similar to *Rh. lineola* (Fabricius, 1794)). Eyes in male holoptic.

Type material of *Rhagio aterrimus* sp. nov.

Holotype: SPAIN: Segovia, Puerto de Navacerrada, 40.789°N 4.006°W, 1-VI-2016, 1913 m, 1 ♂, leg. P. Álvarez Fidalgo, Col. MNCN reference nr. MNCN_Ent 169457. Specimen pinned.

Paratypes: SPAIN: Segovia, San Ildefonso, unknown coordinates, VI-1902 (unknown exact date), about 1200 m, 1 ♂, leg. unknown, specimen from collection Seebold and donated to MNCN Col. MNCN reference nr. MNCN_Ent 169501 [specimen erroneously identified as *Rhagio funebris* by Gil Collado]; SPAIN: Segovia, Puerto de Navacerrada, 40.791°N 4.008°W, 1878 m, 26-V-2015, 3 ♂, 1 ♀, leg. P. Álvarez Fidalgo, Col. MNCN reference nr. MNCN_Ent 171927 (♂), MNCN_Ent 171928 (♂), MNCN_Ent 173859 (♂) (extracted genitalia) and MNCN_Ent 173858 (♀), 1 ♂, leg. P. Álvarez Fidalgo, Col. CTZS; SPAIN: Segovia, Puerto de Navacerrada, 40.789°N 4.006°W, 1-VI-2016, 1913 m, 3 ♂, 1 ♀, leg. P. Álvarez Fidalgo, Col. MNCN reference nr. MNCN_Ent 169458 (♂), MNCN_Ent 169459 (♂), MNCN_Ent 169460 (♂) and MNCN_Ent 169461 (♀). All specimens are pinned.

Other material

PORTUGAL: Serra da Estrela, Nave de Santo Antonio, 6-V-2007, 1 ♀, photograph, originally published as *Rhagio niger* on www.diptera.info (ALMEIDA, 2007; 2010). This location is relatively high in the Serra at 1550 m altitude.

Description of *Rhagio aterrimus* sp. nov.

Male (Figs. 2-4 and 15b):

- **Size:** Length 5.8 mm (excluding antennae), wing length 5.0 mm.
- **Head:** Eyes holoptic, facets of one size. Parafacialia and gena with very long, black hairs. Occiput largely or completely covered with black hairs, in some specimens a few light hairs present at lower margin. Clypeus dark brown, slightly higher than broad in frontal view, reversed pear-shaped; proboscis short. Apical segment of palpus black, elongated, gradually tapering, about four times as long as largest width, covered with very long black hairs, their length approaching length of apical segment of palpus.
Antenna black, first antennal segment about square, with long black hairs above and below (much longer than first antennal segment), second segment short (its length less than its width), with somewhat shorter black hairs, third segment relatively short, almost bare, with convex margin in lateral view (Fig. 15b). Arista bare and long, nearly twice as long as basal three antennal segments together, in lateral view implanted on third antennal segment almost apically.
- **Thorax:** Scutum, scutellum and pleuron very dark grey, nearly black. Scutum with a pair of not so sharply marked light grey sublateral vittae, postpronotum slightly lighter grey. Scutum and scutellum with long, erect, black hairs. Proepisternum (propleuron) and proepimeron covered with black hairs, anepisternum with a large field of black hairs on posterior third, katatergite with long black hairs, otherwise pleuron bare. Halter black.
- **Legs:** Completely black with black hairs [in alcohol, the tibiae are reddish in the middle]. Coxae with long black hairs. Tibiae, especially hind tibia, strongly laterally compressed, hind metatarsus laterally compressed as well.

Fig. 3: *Rhagio aterrimus* sp. nov. Male in its natural habitat, Puerto de Navacerrada, Madrid, Spain, 1-VI-2016, (ÁLVAREZ, 2016).

<http://www.biodiversidadvirtual.org/insectarium/Rhagio-aterrimus-Zeegers-y-Alvarez-Fidalgo-2016-img805052.html>

- **Wing:** More or less uniformly brown including alula, stigma darker. Venation as usual for the genus, however, anal cell narrowly open or closed at wing margin. Basal branch of anal vein (vein A₂) narrowly following the wing margin, hence strongly curved near apex. Calypter dark.
It should be noticed that there is a remarkable variation in wing veins, especially of the veins normally leaving the discal cell apically. Fig. 7 gives an overview of the variation found. In many cases, the venation of both wings differ qualitatively. It is not a phenomenon restricted to one population: also the specimen from Portugal exhibits an aberrant wing venation. This degree of variation in *Rh. aterrimus* is extraordinary, since wing venation is considered generally to vary very little within one species (STARK *et al.*, 1999).
- **Abdomen:** Completely black, relatively short, each segment at least twice as broad as long, tergites with long hairs, those on tergite 1 and lateral parts of tergites 2-3 with long yellow hairs, remainder with shorter black hairs. First sternite (Fig. 1) fully covered with long, yellowish-white hairs, anterior part of second sternite bare, posterior part and following two sternites with yellow hairs, apical sternites with black hairs.
- **Terminalia:** Sternite 8 very short, about four times as broad as long, in situ even looking shorter. Hypandrium convexly triangular as common to male *Rhagio* (ROZKOŠNÝ & SPITZER, 1965). Inner margin of basistylus in ventral view convex in the middle. Dististylus relatively narrow and strongly curved.

Fig. 4: *Rhagio aterrimus* sp. nov. Male, a-b: holotype (scale bar = 1 mm); c-h: paratype. a: habitus, dorsal; b: habitus, lateral; c-d: head (scale bar = 0.5 mm), c: frontal; d: lateral; e-h: male genitalia (scale bar = 0.1 mm), e: genitalia in situ, dorsal; f: genitalia extracted, dorsal; g: genitalia in situ, ventral; h: genitalia extracted, ventral. Note the aberrant wing venation in the right wing.

Female (Figs. 5-6):

Generally very similar to male, different as follows: eyes dichoptic, broadly separated, frontal stripe yellowish-brown, downwards slightly divergent, nearly twice as high as broad at base. Hairs on abdomen shorter than in male.

Fig. 5: *Rhagio aterrimus* sp. nov. Female, paratype; a-b: habitus (scale bar = 1 mm), a: dorsal; b: lateral; c: head, frontal (scale bar = 0.5 mm). Note the lacking crossvein at apex of discal cell in both wings, i. e. discal cell lacking.

Etymology: This new species is named due to its very dark appearance, much darker than any other dark *Rhagio*, *Rh. niger* included. Since the colouration is dull black rather than shining, we prefer *aterrimus* (very dull-black) over *nigerrimus* (very shiny-black).

Fig. 6: *Rhagio aterrimus* sp. nov. Female in its natural habitat, Puerto de Navacerrada, Segovia, Spain, 26-V-2015, (ÁLVAREZ, 2015).

<http://www.biodiversidadvirtual.org/insectarium/Rhagio-aterrimus-Zeegers-y-Alvarez-Fidalgo-2016-img754073.html>

Ecology: The type locality of *Rh. aterrimus* (Puerto de Navacerrada) consists primarily in pine woodlands (*Pinus sylvestris*) with several stony paths (Fig. 8). Other vegetation in the area, particularly by the paths, are species of Broom (*Cytisus oromediterraneus*), Juniper (*Juniperus communis*) and bushes of bramble (*Rubus* sp.). Part of the area belongs politically to Comunidad de Madrid and other part to Comunidad de Castilla-León but the natural vegetation is extremely similar in both sides of the border.

The specimens were observed in the same locations in 2015 and 2016. In both years they were present in good numbers (surprisingly, nearly all males) by several paths that cross the woods, both in the Segovian and Madrilean side of the area.

In 2015, the species was seen on the 26th of May. The day was sunny but cool and windy (altitude ranging from 1750 to about 1920 m., temperature about 12 °C) which might be the reason of the very limited activity of the species, males walking awkwardly on the ground. Only one female was found sitting on leaves of an unidentified plant at ground level (Fig. 6).

In 2016 the species was found on the first of June with sunny and pleasant temperatures (about 25 °C) and individuals were rather active, males chasing each other in short flights at ground level and perching on stones on the ground or on rocks by the paths. Only two females were found this year, one specimen being chased by 2-3 males in short flights around a bolder by one of the paths and the flies sitting on it every now and then.

Fig. 7: Wings of *Rhagio aterrimus* sp. nov. (scale bar = 1 mm). a: normal wing; b: aberration with vein M_2 originating from vein M_1 (not from discal cell) and with vein M_3 truncated; c: aberration with crossvein m-m lacking, hence discal cell open; d: idem and aberration with a looping in vein M_1 .

Fig. 8: Type locality of *Rhagio aterrimus* sp. nov. (Photo: Piluca Álvarez Fidalgo)

***Rhagio niger* (Wiedemann, 1820)**

Figs. 9 and 15c

Leptis niger Wiedemann: WIEDEMANN in MEIGEN (1820): 98.

Rhagio niger Wiedemann apud Meigen: LINDNER (1925): 23.

Rhagio niger Wiedemann: SZILÁDY (1934): 242.

Rhagio niger (Wiedemann in Meigen): MAJER (1988): 22; CARLES-TOLRÁ (2002): 111.

Note on nomenclature: MEIGEN (1820) explicitly mentioned Wiedemann as author of this species; hence the correct name reads *Rhagio niger* (Wiedemann, 1820).

Material of *Rhagio niger* (Wiedemann, 1820)

Typus male (col. ZMHB), labelled: “[small blue square label (empty)] / Lusitan. Hffmsg [in writing] / 4214 [printed] / nigra Hffgg. * Wied [same writing] / Typus [orange label; printed] / Zool. Mus. Berlin [printed]”.

This type is in good condition: the left hind leg is missing and the abdomen is artificially laterally compressed. The number refers to the catalogue of the “Alte Sammlung” (Ziegler, in litt.). Wiedemann (1820) described this species [in our translation] “from Portugal; in Hoffmannsegg’s collection”, without indication of the number of specimens.

Ziegler (in litt.) kindly informed us about the material present in the collection ZMHB. All other specimens present there bear a label “Coll. Loew”. It is unclear whether Wiedemann had seen this material. Although this seems unlikely, recommendation 73F of the Code (INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON ZOOLOGICAL NOMENCLATURE, 1999) clearly states that rather than assume a holotype we should select a lectotype. Given the evidence presented and the generally good state of the specimen studied by us, we hereby designated it as lectotype and label it accordingly.

SZILÁDY (1934) records this species from “Amasien” [currently: Amasya, Turkey] and “Africa” in col. Wien. Recorded from Italy without source by MAJER (1988).

Diagnosis: Eyes in male strongly dichoptic. First two antennal segments nearly bare, with a few short black hairs dorsally. Hairs on parafacialia and occiput white. Palpus brown. Scutum grey with a pair of lighter vittae. Anepisternum bare except for a few black hairs on upper margin. Wings darkened, halter yellow. Abdomen reddish brown. Femora dark with lighter apices, tibiae reddish.

Redescription of *Rhagio niger* (Wiedemann, 1820)

Male (Figs. 9 and 15c):

- **Size:** Length 7.5 mm (excluding antennae), wing length 8.5 mm.
- **Head:** Eyes strongly dichoptic, facets of one size. Frontal stripe grey, virtually parallel sided, about four times as high as broad at base. Parafacialia with longer yellowish and a few dark hairs. Gena and occiput covered with long white hairs, upper half of occiput just behind eye with 2-3 irregular rows of black hairs. Clypeus silvery grey, slightly higher than broad in frontal view; proboscis short. Apical segment of palpus brown, elongated, gradually tapering, about four times as long as largest width, covered with long black and white hairs. Antenna greyish brown, first antennal segment about square, dorsally with a few very short black hairs, second and third segment short (its length less than its width), second segment with even smaller hairs, third bare, its dorsoapical margin in lateral view convex, with hairs even smaller (Fig. 15c). Arista bare and long, nearly twice as long as basal three antennal segments together, in lateral view placed on the third antennal segment almost apically.

Fig. 9: *Rhagio niger* (Wiedemann, 1820). Male, lectotype; a-b: habitus (scale bar = 1 mm), a: dorsal; b: lateral; c: head and thorax, lateral (scale bar = 0.5 mm); d: head, frontal (scale bar = 0.1 mm); e-f: genitalia in situ (scale bar = 0.1 mm); e: dorsal; f: ventral.

- **Thorax:** Scutum, scutellum and pleuron dark grey, scutum with a pair of light grey sublateral vittae, postpronotum silvery grey. Proepisternum (propleuron) and proepimeron covered with white hairs, anepisternum bare except for a few black hairs on upper margin, katatergite with long white hairs, otherwise pleuron bare. Halter yellow. .
- **Legs:** Coxae grey as pleuron and with long light hairs, femora brown, apically yellow, tibiae cylindrical, yellow, mid and hind tibiae with 2 strong ventral apical setae each, tarsi darker than tibiae.
- **Wing:** More or less uniformly yellowish-brown except for brown costal cell, even browner stigma and transparent alula. Wing venation as usual for the genus, anal cell narrowly opened or just closed

on wing margin, vein R_1 covered with setulae as strong as those on costa, basal branch of anal vein (vein A_2) almost straight, not following the wing margin. Calypter white with yellow margin.

- **Abdomen:** Elongated, first visible segment short, segments 2-4 longer than broad, tergites reddish brown with a hint of black central maculae, anterior sternites yellowish brown, more posterior ones turning chestnut brown, so generally less black than both *Rh. aterrimus* and *Rh. funebris*. Tergites and sternites covered with short light hairs, from fourth segment on laterally with short black hairs. First sternite with white hairs, anterior part of second sternite bare.
- **Terminalia** [in situ, not extracted]: Sternite 8 large, nearly as long as wide at apex, nearly completely covering the hypandrium. Inner margin of basistylus distinctly concave over whole its length. Dististylus rather straight.

Female:

Unknown to us. SZILÁDY (1934) mentions a female in col. NHMW.

***Rhagio funebris* (Meigen, 1820)**

Figs. 10-12 and 15a

Leptis funebris Meigen: MEIGEN (1820): 98.

Rhagio funebris (Meigen): LINDNER (1925): 19; SÉGUY (1926): 104; SZILÁDY (1934): 240; MAJER (1988): 22; NARCHUK (1988): 689.

MEIGEN (1820) describes this species from an unknown locality based on one male specimen (“ein Männchen aus der Baumhauerischen Sammlung”). In the Meigen collection, currently in MNHN, there are two specimens labelled as types, with catalogue numbers ED3213 and ED3214. Only the first specimen bears a label with “*Leptis funebris* ♂” in (apparently) Meigen’s writing (Fig. 10d). The other specimen is not in full agreement with the original description. Therefore, we consider the specimen labelled ED3213 in MNHN to be the holotype. Since only one specimen is mentioned in the description, ED3214 is not a (syn)type.

Material of *Rhagio funebris* (Meigen, 1820)

Holotype male (col. MNHN), from the Meigen collection with Catalogue number ED3213, studied from photographs available (MUSÉUM NATIONAL D’HISTOIRE NATURELLE, 2015).

MNCN: 2 ♂ and 1 ♀ collected in Florence, Italy on 26th May (year unknown). Collector unknown. Specimens in good conditions.

Diagnosis: Eyes in male strongly holoptic. Third antennal segment distinctly concave dorsoapically in lateral view. Hairs on parafacialia and occiput mainly white. Palpus, scutellum and abdomen entirely greyish dark. Scutum without or with a pair of greyish vittae, in the latter case these are not strongly marked. Anepisternum with black hairs on posterior third and just a few ones on the remaining upper area. Wings darkened. Halter yellow. Femora dark, pale at apex in front and mid femora, tibiae yellowish.

Redescription of *Rhagio funebris* (Meigen, 1820)

Male (Fig. 10):

Fig. 10: *Rhagio funebris* (Meigen, 1820). Male, a-d: holotype [courtesy MNHN]; e-g: specimen from Florence, Italy. a-b: habitus (scale bar = 2 mm), a: dorsal; b: lateral; c: head, frontal (scale bar = 0.1 mm); d: labels; e: head and thorax, lateral (scale bar = 0.5 mm); f-g: genitalia in situ (scale bar = 0.1 mm); f: dorsal; g: ventral.

Fig. 11: *Rhagio funebris* (Meigen, 1820). Female, specimen from Florence; a-b: habitus (scale bar = 1 mm), a: dorsal; b: lateral; c: head, frontal; d: thorax, left lateral view, showing hairy anepisternum (scale bar = 0.1 mm).

- **Size:** Length 6.2 mm (excluding antennae), wing length 5.6 mm.
- **Head:** Eyes strongly holoptic, facets of one size. Parafacialia with mainly pale hairs mixed with a few dark ones. Gena and occiput covered mainly with long white hairs. Clypeus silvery grey, slightly higher than broad in frontal view; proboscis short. Palpus dark with black long hairs. Antenna brownish grey, first antennal segment about square with long black hairs (longer than first antennal segment), second segment shorter (its length less than its width), and third one longer beneath than in the upper area, in the front, slightly moon-shaped, as a consequence the antero-dorsal margin is distinctly concave in lateral view (so, remarkably similar to the antenna of *Rhagio*

scolopaceus (Linnaeus, 1758)), both last segments also with hairs, particularly longer on the top area of the third segment (Fig. 15a); arista long, nearly twice as long as basal three antennal segments, bare.

- **Thorax:** Scutum, scutellum and pleuron darkish grey. Scutum and scutellum with long, erect, black hairs, and with a pair of not very sharply marked light grey sublateral vittae, which seem to be very variable in intensity (from clearly marked to hardly visible). Anepisternum with some black hairs on upper part and denser on posterior third, katatergite with long pale hairs, otherwise pleuron bare. Halter yellow.
- **Legs:** Coxae grey as pleuron, with long pale hairs. All femora dark, front and mid femora apically yellow, tibiae and tarsi yellowish.
- **Wing:** More or less uniformly darkened with browner stigma.
- **Abdomen:** Very dark. Anterior part of tergites 2 and 3 tend to be more brownish than the rest, which are clearly dark. Anterior sternites also brownish, more posterior ones turning dark. First sternite with white hairs, anterior part of second sternite bare, posterior part also with pale hairs.
- **Terminalia** [in situ, not extracted]: Sternite 8 large, nearly as long as wide at apex, nearly completely covering the hypandrium. Inner margin of basistylus very slightly concave, almost straight. Dististylus relatively narrow and strongly curved towards inside.

Fig. 12: *Rhagio funebris* (Meigen, 1820). Female in its natural habitat, Angera, Varese, border of Lago Maggiore, Italy, 11-VI-2015. (Photo: Philippe Moniotte)

Female (Figs. 11-12):

Generally similar to male, but for the eyes, which are dichoptic and broadly separated. Frontal stripe silvery-greyish, downwards slightly divergent, nearly twice as high as broad at base.

We have seen only material from Italy. Recently, a female was photographed by Philippe Moniotte at Lago Maggiore in northern Italy at 193 meters a. s. l. (Fig. 12). NARCHUK (1988) records this species from the Caucasus.

Remark: The following three species are similar to *Rh. funebris* in having totally dark scutum, scutellum and pleuron and yellow halter: *Rhagio chrysopilaeformis* (Bezzi, 1898) from central Italy, *Rhagio corsicanus* Becker, 1910 from Corsica and *Rhagio idaeus* Bezzi, 1908 from Crete. All these three species lack uniformly darkened wings. *Rh. chrysopilaeformis* and *Rh. idaeus* also differ from *Rh. funebris* by the white-haired palpus; *Rh. corsicanus* is very similar to, if not identical to, *Rh. funebris*. We have not seen these species.

***Rhagio cingulatus* (Loew, 1856)**

Fig. 13

Leptis cingulata Loew: LOEW (1856): 28.

Leptis cingulatus Loew: SCHINER (1862): 172.

Rhagio cingulatus (Loew): LINDNER (1925): 17; SZILÁDY (1932): 45; SZILÁDY (1934): 243; MAJER (1988): 22; NARCHUK (1988): 688.

Rhagio freyae Lindner: LINDNER (1923): 8.

Fig. 13: *Rhagio cingulatus* (Loew, 1856). Female in its natural habitat, Niederthai, Ötztal, Tyrol, Austria (1.500 m), 10-VIII-2010. (Photo: Claudia Brückner)

This species (Fig. 13) is found at higher altitudes in the Alps, both above and below the timberline (SCHINER, 1862; LINDNER, 1923, 1925; SZILÁDY, 1934; SCHACHT, 1994). It is very rare in Slovakia

(ROZKOŠNÝ & SPITZER, 1965). If the record from Legnica (“Leignitz”) in western Poland by SZILÁDY (1932) is correct, this must refer to the nearby Sudety mountains.

Remark: *Rhagio rondanii* Bezzi, 1908 is very similar to *Rh. cingulatus*. The male differs by the dichoptic eyes. Females cannot be differentiated.

***Rhagio fuscipennis* (Meigen, 1820)**

Fig. 14

Leptis fuscipennis Meigen: MEIGEN (1820): 97; SCHINER (1862): 172.

Rhagio fuscipennis (Meigen): LINDNER (1925): 19; SZILÁDY (1932): 45; SZILÁDY (1934): 243; MAJER (1988): 22.

Type from Carinthia (MEIGEN 1820). SCHINER (1862) mentions several specimens from Austria. Recorded for Poland without source by MIKOŁAJCZYK (1991) and from France by MAJER (1988). It seems this highly characteristic species has a restricted distribution.

Fig. 14: *Rhagio fuscipennis* (Meigen, 1820). Male in its natural habitat, Korensko sedlo, Slovenia, 17-VII-2013. (Photo: Tomi Trilar)

Key to dark *Rhagio* with darkened wings

All species of *Rhagio* mentioned above agree in having predominantly dark abdomens and darkened wings.

Here, we present a key to separate these dark species of *Rhagio* with darkened wings. It is a pragmatical key to help identification that does not show phylogenetic affinity. For instance, of *Rh. cingulatus*, only females are included, since the males always have a clearly yellow abdomen with black markings. *Leptis tristis* Schummel, 1837 is based on the original description not a *Rhagio*, but a *Ptiolina* or *Spania*, as already concluded by BECKER (1921). LINDNER (1942) synonymized *L. tristis* with *Ptiolina obscura* (Fallén, 1814) (but did not see the type).

Traditionally, the presence or absence of vittae on thoracic dorsum is considered a feature of major importance (LINDNER, 1925; SZILÁDY, 1934). However, in the case of *Rh. funebris*, this feature is variable. Also in other cases, such as *Rhagio notatus* (Meigen, 1820), the presence of thoracic vittae is variable. In our opinion, there is a gradual transition from clear presence of vittae towards clear absence. Hence, the feature is of relatively little use in a dichotomic key.

Fig. 15: Antennae of male *Rhagio* Fabricius, 1775, lateral view (scale bar = 0.1 mm). a: *Rhagio funebris* (Meigen, 1820); b: *Rhagio aterrimus* sp. nov.; c: *Rhagio niger* (Wiedemann, 1820).

- 1(a) Halter black. Parafacialia and gena covered with black hairs only *Rh. aterrimus* nov. sp.
 1(b) Halter yellow or brownish yellow. Parafacialia and gena predominantly or completely covered with light hairs 2
- 2(a) Palpus yellow with light hairs. Abdomen dark with yellow transverse bands, at least on apical sternites (female) *Rh. cingulatus* Loew
 2(b) Palpus dark to black, usually with predominantly black hairs. Abdomen dark, usually unbanded, sometimes anterior tergites brownish 3
- 3(a) Scutellum largely or completely yellow. Femora black and yellow *Rh. fuscipennis* Meigen
 3(b) Scutellum largely or completely dark. Femora dark (at most extreme apex lighter) 4
- 4(a) Antennal segments with long hairs, third segment elongated, its dorsoapical margin distinctly concave. Arista inserted below middle in lateral view (Fig. 15a). Male: eyes holoptic
 *Rh. funebris* Meigen
 4(b) Antennal segments with only some very short hairs, third segment short, its dorsoapical margin convex. Arista inserted at middle in lateral view (Fig. 15c). Male: eyes strongly dichoptic *Rh. niger* Wiedemann

Discussion

We have described a new species of *Rhagio*, found in the mountains of Spain and Portugal; hence it seems quite restricted in distribution. This is a common pattern in *Rhagio*. Of the about 40 species from the western Palearctic we currently consider valid, about half are very restricted in distribution; most of these appear to be only known from the types. Whether this reflects the true situation or is an artifact of our limited knowledge of the genus, remains an open question for now.

Several species of *Rhagio* are traditionally characterized by the dichoptic eyes in the male, for instance *Rhagio cavannae* (Bezzi, 1898), *Rhagio latipennis* (Loew, 1856), *Rh. niger* and *Rh. rondanii*. These species are not closely related. Apparently, dichoptism is a rather plastic feature in *Rhagio*; it has originated several times independently. The feature should therefore be used with some care.

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